

Impact of virtual learning on Student's Academic Achievements during COVID19 ...

Impact of virtual learning on Student's Academic Achievements during COVID19 outbreak: A Case Study

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Abstract

A virtual learning platform is an online-based podium that provides digital solutions to learners and academicians to improve their learning experience. Virtual learning is a system that provides educators a digital-based options for producing interactive lessons. Since the early days of the COVID19 pandemic, Universities throughout the world took rapid initiatives to ensure students' learning continuity and secure the well-being of their learners. (Alsoud & Harasis, 2021)

Virtual learning is a form of learning that uses technology. A learning system based on dignified teaching, with the help of digital resources is known as virtual learning. This study aims To find out the impact of virtual learning on student's academic achievements during COVID-19 outbreak. The recent research study was carried to explain the existing conditions of the learners' views and concepts. M.Phil and Ph.D. scholars that were confined to "The Faculty of Education, University of Sindh". Descriptive Survey design was used to collect data from the respondents, from which 200 respondent's feedback was recorded and elaborated with the proper and timely usage of tool (Questionnaire). The data was collected by the researcher himself by visiting institution. A five point Likert scale was used to collect the data and hypotheses was tested using regressions Analysis in SPSS 23.

Keywords: Virtual learning, COVID-19 outbreak, Academic Achievements.

Introduction

Virtual learning is a fast track to approach the instructor and instructional material. The Covid-19 pandemic attack had paralyze education and the virtual learning was the only source to develop the educational system. Virtual learning maintained its viability as a technique of ensuring rapid information dissemination and transfer while being accessible

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over the internet. Virtual learning refers to students' online access to teachers and interconnectivity that is still dependent on information technology (Bernal et al., 2020).

In times of natural calamities and difficulties, virtual learning has remained a critical necessity to aid educational institutions in spreading instructional activities. The (HEC) higher education commission advised using a virtual learning system during this critical situation of natural disaster, like this COVID-19, which may be useful in mobilizing digital classrooms and covering distant learning activities of students during outbreaks and lockdowns. In addition, HEC pushes institutions to invest in distant learning technological infrastructure. Pakistan confronts both challenges and possibilities in its efforts to become a digital country. (Mahyoob, 2020)

It was strictly instructed to shift on virtual learning hence, the institutions created an online learning environment and instructed affiliated institutions to undertake virtual learning activities throughout the country to avoid education loss during the COVID-19 crisis (Akbar Malik, 2014). The main challenges that institutions faced in ensuring an appropriate and approachable system of education that could be possible for the learners. In Pakistan it was difficult to switch on virtual learning in such a short span of time because of traditional infrastructure and poor information technology system (IT). It was definitely impossible for the developing countries such as Pakistan to grasp of such a hard situation. A developing country like Pakistan it was too hard to take an initiative for virtual learning system of education on immediate and crucial basis in order to emerge virtual teaching and learning practices (Mahyoob, 2020).

Different universities of Pakistan shifted their teaching and learning process on virtual learning, owing hardships in the digital paradigm in Pakistan. The University of Sindh Jamshoro is one of those universities who had strived a lot to convey the educational assets to the real deserving individuals on their end. Despite the higher education commission's (HEC) statement, institutions have encountered detentions and difficult obstacles owing to a lack of information technology infrastructure and students' skill in technological usage and acceptance of new systems. Virtual learning is actually demonstration of the modern system of internet usage for the purpose of teaching and learning which is actually based on the presence of the material resources. It depends on financial resources, without financial resources the material of virtual learning like computers and other necessary accessories cannot be arranged. Whereas, the infrastructure of the school and university level is not such a satisfactory where these resources could be used and applied. On the other hand human resource is also a huge problem for the Pakistani institutions, where the teachers are not trained on that extent that they could shift whole of the teaching and learning on virtual or online system. The importance of technology cannot be ignored in today's scientific era of globalization, where it is embraced across all institutions, including the education sector, which prioritizes the function of virtual learning during pandemic outbreaks throughout the world (Amrithesh & Jeayaram, 2019).

Originating innovative technologies and learning management systems in the areas of teaching and assessment have advanced, giving a user-friendly option for educators and allowing policymakers (Ong, 2020).

The modern technology of the 21st century has added the importance of virtual learning. The management of the educational system and the teaching and learning process has been very

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difficult without usage of modern technology. It is indeed a crucial time for any nation of the world to shift and continue with modern technology. In this regard all the resources like human, material and financial resources are needed to be used with high spirit to grasp over the gap of the technology usage, in this COVID-19 pandemic, it has been now a need of time to employ information technology to cover coursework during required time (Alsoud & Harasis, 2021).

Statement of the problem

All the universities of Pakistan are now striving to shift on virtual teaching and learning system. It is endeavored to reshape their system of instruction by moving towards virtual learning. The crucial time for moving towards virtual learning bears different issues ahead regarding administrative and academic sides of these universities (Mahyob, 2020).

In this regard the Faculty of Education, university of Sindh was selected to investigate impact of virtual learning on students' academic achievements during COVID19 outbreak, as it is a big challenge for all universities to shift on virtual learning during COVID19 Outbreak on a large scale throughout Pakistan.

Objective of the study

1. To find out the impact of virtual learning on student's academic achievements during COVID19 outbreak.

Hypotheses

1. Ho There is no significant impact of virtual learning on student's academic achievements during COVID19 outbreak

Significance of the study

This study will be helpful

- 1) In understanding the implication of virtual learning.
- 2) To improve the academic achievements of the students, by using virtual learning.
- 3) This study will be helpful for the researchers for conducting research on virtual learning and seeking further guidance.
- 4) This study will be helpful for the educational institutions to enhance the students' learning outcomes by using modern technologies.
- 5) This study will be helpful for the educational institutions to maintain and enhance their standards of modern educational system.
- 6) This study will help the teachers to grasp over the gaps of virtual learning.
- 7) This study will be helpful for the students to make themselves more effective learners by applying modern technology in learning.
- 8) This study will be helpful for the guidance of policy makers to bring some reforms in teachers' skills by ICT trainings.
- 9) This study will be helpful for the future research in digital learning.
- 10) This study will be helpful for different Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) working for the betterment of education to encompass over the gaps of ICT usage and virtual learning in educational institutions.

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Delimitation of the study

- 1) This study is delimited to the students/scholars of M.Phil, Ph.D.
- 2) This study is confined to only faculty of education, university of Sindh.

Review of Related Literature

Virtual Learning

Virtual learning is considered to be the way of learning with the help of modern technologies. The use of technology enables the learner to reach a broader learning material from each core of the world. The technology resources are very supportive for the learning purpose in this modern era, where the developed countries has shifted whole of their teaching and learning system to virtual system. It is indeed a difficult task for the developing countries to catch the destination and could develop their educational system on online learning, where the resources were hardly managed and lacking behind, such as human, material and financial resources.

Now the virtual learning has been greatly influence by the outbreak of COVID-19. The online system of education is on its peak, more and more people are shifting their methods of learning by switching on virtual learning. The college and the university students use internet in respect of their area of the study, as it is easy to catch the recent and updated learning material, specially the research scholars have encompassed over that gap (Karimnia & Kay, 2015).

UTAUT model

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) tend to let the learners know whether the use of the technology is accepted or rejected and at what extent it can be improved. It was presented priority in two case studies where the model was found successful and got high popularity. In this research case study this model helped in covering the extent of virtual learning and its usefulness (Williams et al., 2015). The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model (Venkatesh et al 2003) was used in this research study for the effective use of virtual learning, as it was a crucial time to implement the virtual learning to get the better outcomes of the education during complete lock down period. It was a hard time for survival of the human being as well. In that condition the educational activities were hardly could be continued, therefore it was a dire need of time to be shifted on virtual learning system with the adequate use of information communication technology (ICT). This model of The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) lets the learners as well as instructors to get into the utilization of information communication technology (ICT) smoothly. It was used by the researcher to identify their strengths and weaknesses in the utilization of information communication technology (ICT). The use of information communication technology (ICT) has a great influence in students` academic and instructional material and the practices of research work had been greatly influenced by the usage of information communication technology (ICT) (Attuquayefio & Addo, 2014).

Alves et al., (2017) stated that the use of technology has a positive correlation with the students` academic achievement. The students` knowledge increases when they get into the

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touch of a broader set of material concerned to their studies using information communication technology (ICT). The virtual learning system of education has shifted learning toward self-study in which different social sites are used for better instruction and related literature has a very easy access. In this research study the virtual learning provides an expanded understanding of the ICT and the impact of virtual learning on students' academic achievement.

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Academic achievement is a level of students' achievement in respect of their expected/desired learning goals. It is the extent on which the learning could be extended. The students' achievement is considered to be the measurement of the learning outcomes which is commonly taken place in the end of teaching and learning process in shape of their grades and marks. Universities are often found interested and engaged in imparting quality education, thus the ratio of the students' academic achievements is found enough high, but the sudden attack of the COVID-19 pandemic had destroyed the whole system of the education. In this regard the most of the universities completely shifted their teaching and learning process on virtual learning. In this way the sudden breakdown of the academic activities could be encompassed on some extent (Gilar-Corbi et al., 2020).

Virtual learning was the only source during the COVID-19 by which the academic activities could be encompassed and further teaching and learning process could be possible to continue. Many theoretical models have been used to find out the impact of virtual learning on students' academic achievement in the framework of this research study. The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model was used, which clears the concept of online learning and the number of constructs to the virtual learning were identified in this situation. In this research study the virtual learning was considered as an independent variable and the achievement variable was considered as dependent variable (Westbrook, 2006).

The planned factor tends to an extent of smoothness to have achieved by users to believe that the use of the technology has no issue and pertains no problem in respect of educational use but the access of the internet perceived a high degree of obstacles in Pakistan and could not be found easy on that extent which it should be.(Strategies, 2018). In such a condition, the planned proportions could not be prevailed. Current research study determine the intention of users to use the virtual learning particular and essentially to know the impact of virtual learning on students' academic achievements in faculty of education, University of Sindh (Hamid et al., 2018).

Different research studies advocated the continuation of virtual learning as it facilitates the remotely residing students and also in those days such as pandemic COVID-19. This online system encourages students to cope up their weaknesses by availing huge access of the learning resources

The recent research study intended to recognize the students' perception, intentions and their view about virtual learning and its impact on students' academic achievement, thus the UTAUT model was used and applied to know at what extent the virtual learning is brought into the practice during the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak lockdown and closures of universities. Meanwhile the views of the scholars of faculty of education, university of Sindh

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was collected about the virtual learning, and it was also enquired about the use of software such as, Zoom, and Google Classroom.

In this research anticipated variables, virtual learning and Students` Academic Achievements were used to identify the students` perception regarding the use of online learning. In different research studies it is found that many individuals found interested in virtual learning (Majoka & Khan, 2017). The validity of the use of virtual learning and modern technology cannot be denied in recent technological era (Georgouli, 2011). The main and essential aim of conducting this research study is to know the impact of virtual learning on students` academic achievement. Below is given the conceptual framework of the study which shows that the impact of virtual learning on students` academic achievement.

Conceptual framework

Conceptual Framework

In the current research study one independent variables virtual learning has its impact on the other dependent variable students` academic achievement either their positive or negative. It is found that the virtual learning has always a positive impact on distance learning (Ahmad et al., 1998).

The designed conceptual framework was developed, in terms of variables, named virtual learning and Students` Academic Achievements from the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh, et al., 2003).

The conceptual framework used to interpret the students` opinion and concept about their academic achievement applying virtual learning (technological acceptance) in respect of its innovative and creative influence.

Research Methodology

The design used in this research study was descriptive type of the research with quantitative approach. The design attempted to collect data from the group of interest of the researcher, for measuring and determining the current status of that population with respect of different variables (Mugenda, 2003). This study design enabled the researcher to study the entire population (M.Phil, and PhD) of faculty of education, university of Sindh, where the data was collected from the respondents PhD, and M.Phil. Scholars. For collection of the data Likert scale 5.0 was used, where the options were indicated as strongly disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Undecided (U), agree (A), and strongly agree (SA) respectively. The regression analysis was used to test hypotheses.

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Data Analysis, Discussion, Recommendations and Conclusion

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	97	48.5
	Female	103	51.5
Age	20-30	159	79.5
	30-40	41	20.5
	Master/Bachelor	171	85.5
Education	M.Phil/ Ph.D.	19	14.5

The demographic characteristics of the respondents show that 48.5% of male scholars and 51.5% of the female scholars participated in this research study while 85.5% of the respondents were enrolled in M.Phil and 14.5% of the respondents were enrolled in Ph.D.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.910 ^a	.827	.826	.52009
a. Predictors: (Constant), VL				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	256.644	1	256.644	948.809	.000 ^b
	Residual	53.557	198	.270		
	Total	310.202	199			
a. Dependent Variable: SAA						
b. Predictors: (Constant), VL						

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

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1	(Constant)	.012	.118		.099	.921
	VL	.944	.031	.910	30.803	.000
a. Dependent Variable: SAA						

Coefficient Correlations ^a			
Model			VL
1	Correlations	VL	1.000
	Covariances	VL	.001
a. Dependent Variable: SAA			

Findings

The above table of linear regression model showing the calculated values e.g, R= .910, F= 948.809, (Beta= .944, t=30.803, sig=.000) found that the values are significant, thus the null hypothesis of the study is rejected. The alternate hypothesis, there is significant impact of virtual learning on students` academic achievements, hence is proved, that there is a positive impact of virtual learning on students` academic achievements.

Discussion

The 200 respondents participated to carry out this research study for analysis of scholars` intention to use online learning. For measuring the consistency of the research instrument Cronbach`s alpha was calculated as 0.801. it was calculated by the analysis of the data using regression analysis in inferential statistics with the support of SPSS 23 Software that there is positive impact of virtual learning on students` academic achievement. The virtual learning has a great influence on students learning and its results are found significant from the students` academic achievements

This research study found that the null hypothesis is rejected, thus the alternative hypothesis accepted, on the basis of the results the researcher recommended the future researchers to broaden their study at large scale, as this research study was restrained to a faculty of education, university of Sindh. The findings of this research study revealed that the virtual learning has a positive impact on students` academic achievements. This study found that there should be a supportive environment for the technology acceptance, and the acceptance of virtual learning system in educational institutions should be strengthened with the facility of proper infrastructure for the adequate use of information technology and encourage computer based literacy that is a dire need to enhance the virtual learning troposphere in different universities of the country.

Conclusion

It is concluded through this research study that the virtual learning had been greatly

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influenced during the COVID-19 outbreak especially at university level, moreover the teaching and learning system using modern technology had got a high priority. The scholars of the faculty of education took a high emphasis on the online means of education, where they intend to observe online system as a relaxed, effective and valuable for their learning activities, this is a very crucial and supportive system to be adopted to get the better outcomes. However it casts more investment in required period of time. However, encouraging virtual learning depends on the presence of the high Information Technology (IT) literacy and the information technology IT material, financial and human resources, where management, supervision and scholarly learning should perceive effective means of learning expertise skills.

Recommendations

Virtual learning has been a dire need of time as, the bookish learning has been so far from the teachers as well as learners. Every individual has switched to digital learning, so the institutions need to focus on digital amenities and should develop digital libraries to facilitate the teaching and learning process. Moreover, different other information communication technological opportunities should be introduced to interpret the innovative technology that could be involved in different practices by multiple users in many institution and organization as, they were affected by the covid-19 pandemic during lockdown.

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